

TAILORED SOLID-LIQUID COMPOSITE FOR ENHANCED COMFORT IN ORTHOTIC INSOLES

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SCIENCE FOR
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INNOVATION

Kia kotahi mai –
Te Ao Pūtaiao me
Te Ao Hangarau

National
Science
Challenges

UNIVERSITY OF
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NEW ZEALAND

CENTRE FOR ADVANCED MATERIALS
MANUFACTURING & DESIGN

Peak pressure points and the plantar pressure distribution have a strong correlation with discomfort and likely regions for injury.

58% of lower-limb amputations in New Zealand are performed on patients with diabetes. Typically, amputations in these patients are preceded with a foot ulcer.

Orthotic insoles aim to even out the plantar pressure distribution to lower the peak pressure points.

Static behavior

- Aim for an even distribution of pressure to lower peak plantar stresses.
- Achieved through custom orthotics with total plantar contact.

Dynamic behavior

- Optimize shock absorption and dynamically redistribute pressure.

Standard Foam Orthotic Insole

SLC Orthotic Insole

Solid

Gyroid lattice structure

+

Fluid

Viscous liquid

=

SLC

Gyroid voids filled with liquid

A SLC allows us to adjust the rate dependent and rate independent response of the structure.

Solid Liquid Composite

Structural Response

- Adjusting the aspect ratio of the unit cell effects the tortuosity.
- Tortuosity has a direct relationship with the permeability of a gyroid, where the more tortuous the structure, the lower the permeability.

	Structural Response	Fluid Response	SLC Response
Numerical Approach	<p>FEA: Compressive response between flat, rigid platens.</p>		
Experimental Approach	<p>Uniaxial compression testing.</p>		

FEA

- FEA was carried out on ABAQUS.
- The gyroid geometry was compressed between two rigid platens.
- The numerical study made it feasible to do an extensive parameter sweep on the gyroid's geometric properties
- The key output from this study was the force-displacement response.

0% Compression

25% Compression

50% Compression

Selective Laser Sintering

- Formlabs 3 Form Printer – Elastic 50A Resin

Validation

Cell Thickness Variation

Cell Size Variation

Structural Response

Validation

Darcy's Law

$$q = -\frac{k}{\mu} \nabla p$$

Parameters to vary included:

- Unit cell size
- Cell thickness
- Aspect ratio

- A gyroid sample was tested in a through-thickness permeability set up.
- The permeability calculated from this experiment was used to validate the numerical models
- Results aligned with numerical results within 10% on average.

- Homogenising the SLC will make parametric studies and large scale modelling feasible.
- It must capture the rate dependant and rate independent behaviour.

- Using ABAQUS, the material is assigned a hyperelastic model and a permeability.
- The SLC geometry is enclosed, and compressed by a hemispherical indenter.
- The main output is the force-displacement data for a variety of indentation speeds.

- Fully enclosed, fluid filled disk samples were printed.
- The SLC liquid is mineral oil.

- SLC samples were tested in a replica set up of the numerical model.
- Each sample was impact tested at 3 different speeds.

- Modelling the SLC using the homogenisation methods described is effective for an extensive parametric study.
- Results must be checked through numerically modelling the non-homogenised geometry, then validated through experimental testing.
- The rate dependant effects of the SLC are capable of providing energy absorption properties and pressure redistribution effects.

Integrating the homogenised model into an optimisation framework to assign properties to different regions of an orthotic insole.

Implementation in a full scale orthotic insole, both numerically and experimentally, to assess its effectiveness compared to a standard foam insole.

